

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Comparative Elemental Analysis of Commercial Functionalized Graphene Nanoplatelets Along the Production Chain With X-Ray Photoelectron and Energy-Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy

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Received: 30 September 2024 | **Revised:** 31 January 2025 | **Accepted:** 4 February 2025

Funding: This work was supported by Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programme, 101092796.

Keywords: commercial graphene | functionalized graphene | graphene inks

ABSTRACT

Graphene has been commercialized for over a decade, primarily in the form of suspensions and inks. In this study, we investigate the properties of graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) and their functionalized derivatives, incorporating fluorine or nitrogen as functional groups (FG). The analysis was conducted on three forms, that is, powders, suspensions, and inks, using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The objective of this work is to establish a rapid and comprehensive systematic approach for elemental analysis of commercial functionalized graphene, which can be used for quality control. Functionalization is employed to tailor the material's physical and chemical properties. In our study, graphene samples, functionalized with fluorine or ammonia in a plasma reactor, were investigated. Both XPS and EDX were applicable for all three forms and showed, in general, similar trends between the three forms, so that both XPS and EDX can be used for quality control of GNPs along the production chain.

1 | Introduction

Graphene is a two-dimensional layer of carbon atoms that are bonded to each other in a hexagonal lattice. With a thickness of only one atom, it is one of the thinnest known materials. The large-scale production of high-quality, defect-free graphene is a significant and labor-intensive challenge. Extensive research has focused on developing large-scale synthesis methods, with key techniques including mechanical exfoliation, chemical vapor deposition (CVD), reduction of graphite oxide, epitaxial growth on SiC, and electrochemical exfoliation [1–5]. In addition to its various applications, graphene is the base of which all other carbon nanomaterials emerges, such as buckyballs (0D), carbon

nanotubes (1D), or stacked on top of one another to produce graphite (3D) [6]. The exceptional and seemingly unreal properties of graphene is the reason behind the immense amount of interest in it [7–11]. These superior properties make graphene a viable candidate for various applications ranging from wearable electronics [12] and energy storage industries [13] to pharmaceutical [14] and medical fields [15]. There are many derivatives of graphene such as graphene oxide (GO), reduced graphene oxide (rGO), graphite, and fluorographene (CF). These derivatives have different properties from pristine graphene [16]. A major advantage of graphene is that its properties could be tailored, depending on several factors such the synthesise method, number of graphene sheets, and its surface modification through

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functionalization. Functionalization occurs when functional groups (FGs) are attached, either through covalent bonding or noncovalent bonding, to the graphene sheets on three major bonding sites which are the basal-plane, the edge sites, and the defect sites in the graphene structure [17]. This can considerably alter the chemical and physical properties of graphene [18]. It is worthy to note that functionalization, unlike doping, does not involve removing any carbon atoms from the graphene lattice. Nevertheless, the functional groups are usually attached to the graphene sheets via covalent bonds. To understand the chemical effect of functionalization on graphene, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) in conjunction with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) can be used.

Since commercialization of graphene, many questions were raised as to whether the product which a customer buys is indeed graphene. This is due to the variety of ways graphene could be produced and the difference in the product's properties. Therefore, efforts are being made to develop simple and reliable methods to analyze graphene and its derivatives. One of the most important measurand of graphene and graphene products is the chemical composition often described as the O/C, or the functional element-to-carbon, ratio. For this purpose, an ISO standard is being developed that proposes XPS as the main method for obtaining the chemical composition of graphene in powders and suspensions — ISO CD TS 23359 [19]. Further, XPS is a powerful tool to measure the chemical states of elements. It can provide valuable information about how the carbon atoms are bonded to each other and to other atoms. Although XPS is widely used to study the chemical states of C, it is difficult to find accurate results in the literature [20]. One reason is that the C 1s sp^2 and sp^3 peaks are particularly challenging to interpret, as they are (at most) 0.5 eV apart, and the C 1s sp^2 peak has an asymmetric peak form. Obviously, this is, especially for graphene-related materials, a significant source of uncertainty for the accurate quantification. Furthermore, the measurement and especially the fitting of high-resolution spectra requires time and requires considerable experience, which finally results in an additional challenge to implement the analysis method in routine quality control. Due to these issues, the above-mentioned documentary standard ISO CD TS 23359 focuses on the elemental analysis with detailed guidance on fitting C 1s as well as measuring chemical states. Another widely used and high-throughput method for elemental analysis is EDX, which is coupled with SEM or TEM devices. Since electron microscopy is a common method for investigating the morphology and size of GNPs, and since it is usually combined with EDX, it is obvious to use EDX for elemental analysis for this type of materials. As far as the quantification of the elemental composition is regarded, its accuracy is more or less altered due to the significant morphological effects of the particulate material and physical restrictions when light elements such as carbon and oxygen are involved. Nevertheless, even as a rough estimate, the quick elemental composition determined by EDX is a valuable result. To avoid these limitations, EDX is often used as a sensitive probe to compare between different samples under the same analysis conditions. Specifically, as in this study, the net peak intensity ratios of oxygen (or the functionalized element) to carbon have been extracted to characterize semi-quantitatively the different materials analyzed.

To take a further step in the elemental analysis of GNPs towards a standardized chemical analysis approach, in this work we compare XPS and EDX results on differently functionalized commercial GNPs to prove whether they lead to comparable results, keeping in mind the corresponding information volumes, i.e. a few tens of nanometers for XPS and roughly 1 μm for EDX with electron excitation at an SEM. The possibilities and the limitations of both methods are discussed. The term “graphene” used in the next sections does not refer to its strict definition; rather, it usually refers to a mixture of carbon structures, such as GNP structures and graphite, as these commercial materials are commonly labelled as “graphene” by the manufacturers.

2 | Material and Methods

The samples under investigation could be divided into three main categories: powders, suspensions, and inks. The powders are the starting material from which the suspensions and the inks are formulated. The functional groups used are F and NH_3 . The unfunctionalized starting materials were placed in a patented and reactor barrel and functionalized in a HDPlas plasma reactor by Haydale Ltd. (Ammanford, UK) [21]. Depending on the desired functionalization fluorine gas or ammonia gas were used as feed gas. The feed gas was introduced into a low-pressure chamber where it was energized and ionized to create a plasma. Gas flow and pressure were regulated by a mass flow controller and metered vacuum source. The reactor barrel acted as a counter-electrode and rotated around the central electrode to facilitate mixing. This kind of reaction process ensures the homogeneity of the starting material and the final product.

For EDX and XPS characterization, the powders were prepared by gently putting and leveling them, using a spatula, onto a recess as part of the sample holder. The suspensions are prepared by dispersing the powders in distilled water (DI) then shaking gently, as prepared commercially. The suspension is then drop-casted onto mirror-like polished silicon wafers (Si wafers) that are pre-cleaned thoroughly in a series of sonication of acetone, isopropanol, and finally DI baths. The drop-casted suspension is then left to dry overnight under low vacuum pressure in a desiccator. The drop-casting process was carried out by drop-casting the suspension at least four times and was controlled with SEM, to produce a highly concentrated spot. The viscous inks were smeared onto Si wafers. The commercial inks consist of 60%–80% diacetone alcohol which acts a solvent and a drying agent, 1%–10% carbon black which enhances conductivity and provide pigmentation as well as prevents the aggregation of graphene sheets, and 1%–10% graphite which was used as a starting material GNPs. This results in the presence of the graphene powders in the inks in a small fraction, that is, below 10%, making it challenging to detect functional groups in low functionalized graphene by EDX and XPS with high signal-to-noise ratio, having known the limits of detection of about a few tenths at-% for both analysis methods. The powders and the inks used were provided by Haydale Composite Solutions, United Kingdom.

The EDX analysis was carried out using a Thermo Fisher spectrometer of type UltraDry SDD (silicon drift detector) with a nominal sensor area of 100 mm^2 , mounted at a Zeiss Supra 40 SEM. Each sample was measured using an acceleration

voltage of the electron beam of 5kV and 15kV, at three different locations, with 300s per measurement. The 5-kV excitation has been used to stay more surface-sensitive and excite better the light elements, and the 15-kV excitation has been used to check for possible metal impurities with a higher sensitivity and going deeper into the sample, that is, >1 μm. One analytical challenge with EDX is to correctly identify some elements emitting characteristic X-ray lines that overlap, such as F K (as the functionalization element) and Fe L series (potentially representing impurity). XPS analysis was conducted using Ulvac-PHI “Quantes” spectrometer (Chanhassen, USA), utilizing Al Kα source emitting at 1486.6eV with an X-ray beam spot size of 100 μm and pass energy of 280eV and a step size of 1eV. The elemental composition in at-% is determined from the peak areas after subtracting Shirley backgrounds and using relative sensitivity factors provided by the manufacturer with MultiPak (9.9.2) Spectrum:ESCA software.

3 | Results and Discussion

The results of the quantitative elemental XPS analysis, expressed in mean atomic percentage, extracted from survey spectra are given in Table 1. The survey spectra are shown in the Supporting Information (Figures S1–S9). One first observation is that the non-functionalized graphene (G) samples showed low-to-zero presence of the functional elements while other impurities were the lowest in the ink form. The XPS analysis of the functionalized graphene powders showed a significantly higher degree of functionalization for the F-functionalized (F) than for the N-functionalized (N) samples. For the F samples, the presence of fluorine in the powder (22.4 at-%) is higher than in the suspension (11.5 at-%) and the ink form (11.6 at-%). It is worth mentioning that high-resolution XPS for F 1s for the F-samples in powder, suspension, and ink forms showed the existence of organic fluorine and the absence of metallic fluorine. In the N samples, the nitrogen content was higher in the powder form than in the other forms, which, independent of the exact type of functionalization, has a roughly similar tendency as for the previous type of functionalized samples. The three major impurities detected by XPS are aluminum (Al), silicon (Si), and iron (Fe), which are all expected from the educts and the production process. All the major impurities are below 3 at-%. The O amount and herewith, the O/C, measured with the XPS analysis was corrected under the assumption that Al, Si, and Fe were oxidized. We assumed Al₂O₃, SiO₂, and Fe₂O₃ as oxides. After subtracting the oxygen atoms, potentially bonded to the impurities, from the total oxygen measured in the sample, the corrected O amount and, hence corrected O/C ratios, was determined. This correction decreased the effective amount of oxygen bound to the graphene-carbon, and, herewith, the O/C ratio, but it did not significantly change the relative differences between powders, suspensions, and inks. Given their limited presence (<2 at-%), exact stoichiometry of impurities cannot be determined via XPS. Theoretical stoichiometry of stable impurity oxides was used to estimate corrected oxygen content in the sample, excluding impurities.

Figure 1 provides a graphical representation of the atomic percent ratios O/C, F/C, and N/C for all samples. The O/C ratio increases consistently from powder to suspension to ink forms in

TABLE 1 | Results of the quantitative XPS analysis, expressed as mean at-% with their relative standard deviation, extracted from the survey spectra of all the samples in all forms. Functional group (FG) is represented by nitrogen for N samples and fluorine for F samples. The dash “-” means not detected or not applicable. “Corrected” means after accounting for the oxides formed by the major impurities.

	C	N	O	Corrected O	F	Al	Si	Fe	O/C	Corrected O/C	FE/C
G	Powder	81.3 ± 0.3	—	15.2 ± 0.1	9.2 ± 0.17	1.4 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.1	—	0.19	0.11	—
	Suspension	79.9 ± 3.4	—	16.8 ± 2.7	11.6 ± 2.1	1.6 ± 0.4	1.4 ± 0.0	—	0.21	0.15	—
	Ink	79.5 ± 2.2	0.6 ± 0.1	19.5 ± 2.4	18.8 ± 1.6	—	0.6 ± 0.3	—	0.25	0.24	—
N	Powder	81.7 ± 0.9	2.9 ± 0.3	12.5 ± 0.2	7.3 ± 0.7	1.1 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.0	0.15	0.09	0.03
	Suspension	80.7 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.5	14.9 ± 1.1	11.3 ± 2	0.7 ± 0.4	1.2 ± 0.2	—	0.18	0.14	0.03
F	Ink	80.0 ± 1.8	1.5 ± 0.0	18.6 ± 1.8	18.6 ± 1.8	—	—	—	0.23	0.23	0.02
	Powder	69.1 ± 0.6	—	5.6 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.4	0.7 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.23	0.08	0.01	0.32
	Suspension	70.4 ± 1.3	—	15.3 ± 2.1	10.3 ± 0.4	11.5 ± 2.1	1.5 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.4	0.22	0.15	0.16
	Ink	73.8 ± 2.6	0.9 ± 0.3	13.1 ± 0.8	11.9 ± 1.0	11.6 ± 1.3	1.5 ± 0.0	—	0.18	0.16	0.16

FIGURE 1 | O/C, F/C, and N/C atom-% ratios (including standard deviation) obtained from XPS for the G, F, and N samples in powder, suspension, and ink forms, (a) as directly quantified with XPS, and (b) after consideration of the O stoichiometry with the other detected elements.

the G and N samples but decreases across the F samples. This trend suggests that the presence of oxygen-containing groups is more pronounced in the liquid-based forms (suspension and ink) compared to the solid powder form in the G and N samples. In the suspension and ink, it is safe to say that there is no oxygen left from the solvents in the samples, as any attached water or remaining resin is completely evaporated with the samples being kept under ultrahigh vacuum before and during the measurements. This indicates that the functionalization with fluorine and nitrogen reduces the extent of oxidation, with fluorine having the most substantial effect (see Figure 1). This decrease in oxygen content is likely due to the substitution of oxygen with fluorine and nitrogen containing atoms on the graphene surface. The F/C ratio in the F samples shows a notable decrease from powder to suspension and remains unchanged between suspension and ink forms. The N/C ratio in the N sample remains relatively stable across its forms. This indicates that nitrogen-functionalized graphene is more stable compared to fluorine, potentially due to less reactivity. The data points out that the degree of functionalization differs significantly in the different forms in which the GNPs were provided. The variations in O/C, F/C, and N/C ratios demonstrate that each functional group interacts differently with the graphene matrix and is influenced by the medium (powder, suspension, ink) in which the graphene is present. Based on these observations, it must be concluded that it is important to measure the chemical composition of functionalized graphene materials in the various forms.

EDX analyses at 5 and 15kV provided an insight on both aspects in the elemental composition: (i) the functionalized (light) element-to-carbon ratio (at 5kV excitation) and (ii) the detection of impurities present in the samples (at 15kV excitation). The existence of Al, Si, and Fe has been clearly identified in all the samples, similar to XPS. Other impurities were also detected (such as Mg and S) at the limit of detection of the EDX and XPS methods and hence not taken into account in either analysis. Generally, the EDX quantification of light elements, such as C, N, O and F, emitting characteristic X-rays below 1keV, is not recommended to be applied, particularly for such particulate samples with a strong surface morphology, using fundamental atomic data which are associated with significantly larger uncertainties than those for the K lines of heavier elements (e.g., 3d metals), and at spectrometer efficiencies which are smaller than for X-ray lines at higher energies. Further, as far as the specific quantification of nitrogen is concerned, this is even more challenging due to the low amount of nitrogen present in the N samples and additional difficulties to extract the N net peak

FIGURE 2 | O/C, F/C, and N/C ratios (including standard deviations) obtained for the G, F, and N samples, in powder, suspension, and ink forms, represented as net X-ray intensity ratios extracted from EDX spectra at 5kV and 35° detection geometry.

area from a peak which is overlapped by the neighboring high X-ray peaks of C K and O K. Thus, no (faulty) atom-% data from EDX are reported in this study, but ratios of the net peak intensities (areas) of the functionalized element-to-carbon are given at defined measurement conditions, that is, 5kV excitation and under the conventional analysis geometry of 35° take-off angle, so that realistic comparisons of FG/C intensity ratios to show semi-quantitatively differences/tendencies between samples can be made.

Figure 2 illustrates the EDX intensity ratios for all samples, as powder, suspension, and inks. First observation, in light of the previous statements and in basic agreement with the XPS analysis, nitrogen is detected at the limit of detection of the method only in the N-functionalized powder, and not at all for the N samples in the suspension and ink forms. Further, significant functionalization with F is detected with EDX in all three preparation forms, that is, powder, suspension, and ink, which is in agreement with the XPS observations, with the remark that EDX addresses (even at 5kV) a significantly deeper material volume (a few hundreds of nanometers) than the surface-sensitive XPS (a few tens of nanometers). The decrease in the fluorine content, in the suspension and ink forms compared to the powder form, that is observed in the XPS (surface-sensitive) and EDX (bulk-sensitive) methods suggests a possible detachment or dilution of fluorine groups in the presence of solvents. This possibly occurs due to the weak sp^2 bonding between carbon and fluorine which

is broken by any disturbance in the system to form a stronger sp^3 carbon-carbon bonding. It should be noticed that the sample preparation from liquid suspension for both EDX and XPS has taken place by drop casting the (functionalized) graphene solution as a compact and micrometer-thick deposition onto a silicon substrate, so that no significant signal from Si could be detected. Striking is the increased O/C intensity ratio measured for the

F-functionalized graphene samples in the suspension form. Further, the same O/C tendency, but of slighter magnitude, is observed also for the starting graphene suspension.

Figure 3 provides a graphical and comprehensive view on the O/C, F/C, and N/C ratios for all samples. The ratios from EDX and XPS show similar trends for all samples. For the

FIGURE 3 | Representation of the O/C, F/C, and N/C ratios of all samples: O/C ratio of (a) G-graphene, (b) F-functionalized graphene, and (d) N-functionalized graphene samples as well as the F/C ratio for (c) F-functionalized graphene and the N/C ratio for (e) N-functionalized graphene. LoD, limit of detection. For a realistic comparability between the two methods, XPS and EDX, the uncorrected XPS data (see Figure 1a) were used.

FIGURE 4 | High-magnification SEM images of G, F, and N samples in three different forms, that is, powder (left column), suspension (middle column), and ink (right column).

G-powder and G-suspension, the XPS and EDX results are consistent with one another as shown in Figure 3a. The value corresponding to the G-ink slightly deviates, which could be attributed to the predominance of the resin and carbon black and low content of graphene in inks. This is true for all inks: G-ink, F-ink, and N-ink. An increase of the O/C ratio was observed from the G-powder over the G-suspension to the G-ink with XPS, with EDX showing similar O/C ratios between suspension and ink. For F-graphene, with the sample in all forms, the O/C and F/C ratios obtained with XPS and EDX are consistent with each other, see Figure 3b and c, respectively. For the N-graphene samples, similar O/C ratios for both methods are observed, see Figure 3d. The N/C ratios, for N-samples, show a similar trend for XPS and EDX, that is, basically decreasing from powders to suspension and to the ink; see Figure 3e. The N-content in the N-powder sample is low, that is, <3 at-%. In inks, that is, after further dilution using DI water or resin and carbon black, N was hardly identified by XPS and EDX. It should be noticed that it is particularly challenging to accurately quantify with EDX “light” elements, such as N, in small concentrations, that emit characteristic X-rays below 1 keV. However, with XPS being more sensitive to the detection of N, it is evident that there are traces of N in the N-suspension and N-ink samples.

The morphology of the samples provides valuable insights and possible support in explaining the data acquired with XPS and

EDX. Figure 4 shows high-magnification SEM images of G, F, and N samples in different forms, powders, suspensions, and inks. The functionalization does not affect the morphology of the GNPs significantly, as observed in former investigations [22]. The graphene flakes are clearly visible in the powder forms in comparison to the corresponding inks, where they are observed only at a few places, which is due to the low fraction of GNPs in the inks. The EDX results show that the F/C and N/C are higher in powder form than in ink form, while O/C is less in powder than in ink form, which is evident in the XPS results as well. One possible explanation to this increase in O/C in ink form, relative to powder form, is that the carbon black does not get oxidized. One further advantage of EDX with an SEM for the analysis of graphene-related 2D materials is the ability of elemental mapping with a sub- μm spatial resolution in a short time, which however was not in the scope of this paper. The same message is prominent from the EDX results, that is: to actively analyze the different forms of functionalized material.

4 | Conclusions

XPS and EDX showed similar trends in the analysis of the elemental composition of graphene and functionalized graphene materials, in form of powder, suspension, and as ink. Both methods, XPS and EDX with SEM, found that the powders showed

the highest degree of functionalization with F and N, and the lowest degree for both types of functionalization for the inks. The oxygen content is for the suspensions and inks higher or similar than for powders. The only difference in the trend of XPS and EDX was observed for the F/C ratio. XPS showed for the suspension a lower F/C ratio than for the powder, while EDX indicated a similar ratio for both powders and suspensions. This can be explained with a detachment of the F by the solvent at the surface, which is not observed by the more bulk-sensitive EDX. For low amounts of N, such as for the N-functionalized materials used in this study, EDX gives only limited information on content of N.

To be noticed as a practical information, both XPS and EDX can provide a valuable evaluation of the elemental composition of GNPs in different forms, that is, powders, suspensions, and inks, in less than 1 h (without degassing), including the analysis. Furthermore, not only the main elements, but also impurities can be easily detected with both methods, if the appropriate conditions for measurement are selected, for example, XPS with high-pass energies and EDX at 15 keV. Here, too, same impurity elements have been found by both methods. The different information depth must be considered when comparing the results of both methods, that is, a few tens of nanometers for XPS and micrometer range for EDX. The chemical information gained from the analysis with both methods, XPS and EDX with SEM, makes the correlative methodical approach a valuable tool for quality control in the production chain of functionalized GNPs from the raw graphene material in powder form to complex products, such as functionalized graphene containing inks. Further chemical investigations are ongoing.

Acknowledgments

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programme under grant agreement no. 101092796 (ACCORDs — Green deal inspired correlative imaging-based characterization for safety profiling of 2D materials). The SEM and EDX measurements were done by Thorid Lange. Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.